

Synthesis of some novel porphyrins

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2,3,6,7-Tetra(2-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-1,4,5,8-tetramethylporphyrin [coproporphyrin II, tetramethyl ester] (9) and 2,3-di(2-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-6,7-dimethoxycarbonylmethyl-1,4,5,8-tetramethylporphyrin [a new synthetic coproporphyrin] (10) were synthesized by condensing 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (5) with 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-5,5'-diformyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane (6) and 3,3'-dicarboxymethyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (8) with 6, respectively. Tetra-substituted pyrroles for synthesizing appropriate dipyrrylmethanes were synthesized in good yields by extension and modification of Knorr synthesis.

Porphyrins are tetrapyrrolic compounds of great biological interest¹ and find industrial uses². We report here synthesis of two important porphyrins, dipyrrylmethanes and pyrroles.

The porphyrins were synthesized by reported methods^{3,4}. Tetra-substituted pyrroles were synthesized by extension and modification of Knorr pyrrole synthesis⁵.

The pyrrole benzyl 5-acetoxymethyl-4-(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-3-methylpyrrole-2-carboxylate (1) was synthesized by reported method⁴. Ethyl 4-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrrole-2-carboxylate (2) and ethyl 5-acetoxymethyl-4-ethoxycarbonylmethyl-3-methylpyrrole-2-carboxylate (3) were synthesized as shown in Scheme 1.

The dipyrrylmethanes dibenzyl 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (4), 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (5) and 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-5,5'-diformyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane (6) were prepared as shown in Scheme 2.

Diethyl 3,3'-di(ethoxycarbonylmethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylate (7) and 3,3'-dicarboxymethyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrylmethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (8) were synthesized from 3 (Scheme 3).

The porphyrins 2,3,6,7-tetra(2-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-1,4,5,8-tetramethylporphyrin (porphyrin A) (9) and 2,3-di(2-methoxycarbonyl-ethyl)-6,7-dimethoxycarbonylmethyl-1,4,5,8-tetramethylporphyrin (porphyrin B) (10) were prepared by the reaction of 5 and 8, respectively, with 6 (Scheme 4).

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Electronic spectra (CHCl_3) were recorded on a Varian Techtron 635 instrument and $^1\text{H NMR}$

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

spectra on a Varian A-60 instrument relative to TMS as internal standard. All the solutions in water-immiscible sol-

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

vents were dried over sodium sulfate prior to evaporation. TLC was carried out on silica gel G (Merck) using ether, chloroform or chloroform-methanol. Kieselgel H type 60 (Merck) silica was used for column chromatography using chloroform : benzene (2 : 3) as eluting solvent. Hydriodic acid (56%) was freshly distilled from red phosphorus and was stabilized by addition of hypophosphorus acid (0.5%).

Ethyl 4-acetyl-5-oxohexanoate⁸ and ethyl 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate⁹ were synthesized by reported procedures.

Synthesis of pyrroles :

Benzyl 5-acetoxymethyl-4(2-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-3-methylpyrrole-2-carboxylate (1) was synthesized as described in literature⁴.

Pyrrole 2 : A solution of sodium nitrite (0.109 mol) in water (25 ml) was added to a stirred and cooled solution of ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml).

The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h below 10° and left overnight at room temperature. To the nitroso compound so obtained, a solution of 3-acetyl-4-oxopentanoate (0.10 mol) in acetic acid (30 ml) was added with stirring followed by zinc dust (15 g) in small portions at 60–65°. After heating the mixture at 90–95° for 2 h, it was poured onto crushed ice. Suspension of the product was decanted from any excess of zinc and separated by filtration. It was washed with cold water and crystallized from aqueous ethanol as colorless needles (12 g, 47%), m.p. 93–94° (Found : C, 61.8; H, 7.2; N, 5.2. C₁₃H₁₉NO₄ requires : C, 61.6; H, 7.5; N, 5.3%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 3.28 (2H, s, CH₂CO₂CH₂CH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, ring methyl), 1.26 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃).

Pyrrole 3 : Lead tetraacetate (9 g) was added in small portions with stirring to a solution of the pyrrole 2 (0.024 mol) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml). After stirring for 3.5 h, the mixture was diluted with ice-cold water and the resulting solid was crystallized from ethyl acetate : light petroleum, (5.3 g), m.p. 83–84° (Found : C, 57.8; H, 6.7; N, 4.4. C₁₅H₂₁NO₆ requires : C, 57.8; H, 6.7; N, 4.5%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.5 (1H, s, NH), 5.04 (2H, s, CH₂OCOCH₃), 4.2 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 3.28 (2H, s, CH₂CO₂CH₂CH₃), 2.2 (3H, s, ring methyl), 2.06 (3H, s, CH₂OCOCH₃), 1.24 (3H, t, OCH₂CH₃).

Synthesis of dipyrromethanes :

Dibenzyl 3,3'-di(2-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrromethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid^{6,7} (4) was prepared by the reported method^{6,7}.

3,3'-Di(2-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrromethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid⁶ (5) : Compound 4 (0.008 mol) taken with palladium on charcoal (10%, 300 mg) in methanol (150 ml) having few drops of trimethylamine, was shaken with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure. Precipitated acid was dissolved in aqueous ammonia, filtered to remove catalyst and diluted with water. Acetic acid (17 N; 20 ml) was added and a white solid was separated after 2 h, (3.5 g), m.p. 185–187° (Found : C, 59.6; H, 6.28; N, 6.0. C₂₃H₃₀N₂O₈ requires : C, 59.7; H, 6.4; N, 6.0%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.25 (1H), 9.28 (1H, NH), 7.44 (2H, s, 2 × COOH), 4.3 (4H, q, 2 × OCH₂CH₃), 3.8 (2H, s, methane protons), 2.58 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂CO₂C₂H₅), 2.36 (3H, s), 2.25 (3H, s, aromatic methyl), 1.34 (6H, t, 2 × OCH₂CH₃).

3,3'-Di(2-ethoxycarbonylethyl)-5,5'-diformyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrromethane⁷ (6) : A suspension of 5 (0.004 mol) in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (6 ml) was refluxed under nitrogen for 0.5 h, then cooled to 0°, benzoyl chloride

(3 ml) added dropwise with stirring at 0° after 15 min, benzene (15 ml) added and the reaction mixture was allowed to return to room temperature. The precipitated imine salt was washed with benzene. Moist solid was added to a aqueous ethanol (500 ml, 50%) containing sodium carbonate (3 g). The stirred solution was warmed on a water-bath for 15 min while benzene azeotrope distilled off then water (50 ml) was added to the hot solution and set aside for 8 h at room temperature. The resulting solid was crystallized from aqueous ethanol, (1.1 g), m.p. 163–165° (lit.⁷ 163–165°) (Found : C, 64.1; H, 7.1; N, 6.4. C₂₃H₃₀N₂O₆ requires : C, 64.1; H, 7.0; N, 6.5%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.28 (2H, s, NH), 9.45 (2H, s, CHO), 4.3 (4H, q, 2 × OCH₂CH₃), 3.3 (2H, s, methane proton), 2.58 (8H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂CO₂C₂H₅), 2.3 (6H, s, 2 × ArCH₃), 1.35 (6H, t, 2 × OCH₂CH₃).

Diethyl 3,3'-di(ethoxycarbonylmethyl)-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrolymethane-5,5'-dicarboxylate (7): The pyrrole 3 (0.016 mol) was heated at 90–95° for 3 h with aq. acetic acid (45 ml; 80%) with stirring. The mixture was then cooled and diluted and the resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol as flat colorless plates, (3.6 g), m.p. 155–156° (Found : C, 61.1; H, 6.9; N, 5.8. C₂₅H₃₄N₂O₈ requires : C, 61.2; H, 6.9; N, 5.7%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.4 (1H), 9.18 (1H, NH), 4.2 (8H, overlapping q, 4 × OCH₂CH₃), 3.85 (2H, methane protons), 3.28 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂CO₂C₂H₅), 2.2 (6H, s, 2 × ring methyl), 1.26 (12H, t, 4 × OCH₂CH₃).

3,3'-Dicarboxymethyl-4,4'-dimethyl-2,2'-dipyrrolymethane-5,5'-dicarboxylic acid (8): A mixture of 7 (0.007 mol), ethanol (20 ml) and NaOH (20 ml; 10%) was refluxed for 2 h. Ethanol was then distilled off, the residue cooled and dissolved in water (40 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was acidified by passing SO₂ at 0°. The yellowish solid obtained was washed with water and dried, (2 g, 87%), m.p. 163–165°d (Found : C, 53.9; H, 4.7; N, 7.3. C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₈ requires : C, 53.9; H, 4.76; N, 7.4%); δ (CDCl₃) 9.4 (1H), 9.18 (1H, NH), 7.44 (4H, s, 4 × COOH), 3.85 (2H, s, methane protons), 3.28 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂COOH), 2.2 (6H, s, 2 × ring methyl).

Synthesis of porphyrins :

Porphyrin A (9) : To 5 (0.0003 mol), trifluoroacetic acid (1–2 ml) was added and kept for 20 min at room temperature to effect decarboxylation. This solution was added to a solution of 6 (0.0003 mol) in glacial acetic acid (75 ml) followed by hydriodic acid (0.5 ml; 56%) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml). The reaction mixture was kept in dark for 4 h. Sodium acetate (0.037 mol) in acetic acid (25 ml) was added to it, aerated for 24 h in dark, distilled under reduced pressure, the residue taken in methanol (80 ml) containing sul-

furic acid (18 M; 4 ml) and left overnight at room temperature. The methanolic solution was then partitioned between chloroform (150 ml) and water (400 ml). The chloroform layer was dried over sodium sulfate and evaporated under reduced pressure. Residue was boiled with absolute alcohol (150 ml) and cooled. The resulting solid was washed with absolute ethanol, dried and crystallized from chloroform/absolute ethanol to give coproporphyrin II tetramethylester, (100 mg, 55%), m.p. 285–288° (Found : C, 67.2; H, 6.5; N, 7.8. C₄₀H₄₆N₄O₈ requires : C, 67.6; H, 6.5; N, 7.9%); λ_{\max} (CHCl₃) (log ϵ) 405 (5.28), 500 (4.14), 536 (3.98), 568 (3.84), 622 nm (3.60); δ (CDCl₃) 9.76 (1H), 9.1 (1H), 10.1 (2H) (methine protons), 4.35 (8H, m, 4 × CH₂CH₂CO₂Me), 3.72, 3.68, 3.62, 3.57, 3.53 (24H, 4 × CO₂CH₃, 4 × ring methyl), 3.25 (8H, t, CH₂CH₂CO₂CH₃).

Porphyrin B (10) : Compound 8 (0.0003 mol) was dissolved in trifluoroacetic acid (1.3 ml) and left for 0.5 h. To this solution 6 (0.0003 mol) dissolved in warm acetic acid (100 ml), after cooling was added. The rest of the procedure was similar to that for the preparation of 9. The product was crystallized from chloroform-methanol, (80 mg), m.p. 180–182° (Found : C, 66.7, H, 6.1; N, 8.2. C₃₈H₄₂N₄O₈ requires : C, 66.8, H, 6.1, N, 8.2%); λ_{\max} (CHCl₃) (log ϵ) 400 (5.19), 497 (4.10), 531 (3.93), 566 (3.76), 620 nm (3.62); δ (CDCl₃) 9.72 (1H), 9.27 (2H), 10.05 (1H) (methine protons), 4.87 (4H, s, 2 × CH₂CO₂CH₃), 4.26 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂CO₂CH₃), 3.77, 3.70, 3.67, 3.62, 3.58, 3.53 (24H, 4 × CO₂CH₃; 4 × ring methyl), 3.2 (4H, m, 2 × CH₂CH₂CO₂CH₃).

References

1. N. G. Angeli, G. Lagorio, E. A. San Roman and L. E. Diceli, *Photochem. Photobio.*, 2000, **72**, 49; T. Ogawa and A. Osaka, *Synlett*, 1999, **1**, 62.
2. R. Bonnett, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1995, **24**, 19.
3. G. P. Aresenault, E. Bullock and S. F. MacDonald, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 4348.
4. P. S. Clezy, T. T. Hai and P. C. Gupta, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, **29**, 393.
5. V. Singh, A. Baqi and P. C. Gupta, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 269.
6. A. W. Johnson, E. Markham, R. Price and K. B. Shaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 4256.
7. P. S. Clezy, A. J. Liepa and A. W. Nichol, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1969, **22**, 229.
8. E. Bullock, A. W. Johnson, E. Markham and K. B. Shaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1430.
9. J. B. Garner, G. A. Reddick and G. J. Fink, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 668.